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HONEY BEE *APIS MELLIFERA* L. PATHOGEN SPILLOVER
TO WILD POLLINATORS IN NORTH ITALY

*Impatto dello spillover dei patogeni di Apis mellifera
su impollinatori selvatici nel Nord Italia*

The decline of pollinators is receiving increasing attention, for which pathogens are one of the main responsible (DALMON *et al.*, 2021). Among them, honey bee *Apis mellifera* L. pathogen transmission seems to play an important role in this decline. Although only a little information is available about the effect on wild pollinators, the interspecific transmission may occur in arthropods sharing the same environment with honey bees, or by direct contact with contaminated pollen and nectar during their foraging activity (NANETTI *et al.*, 2021).

This study aimed to investigate the presence and circulation of 21 honey bee pathogens in wild pollinators in seven sites in two Italian northern regions (Emilia-Romagna and Piedmont), evaluating the risk of interspecific transmission and spillover. In each site, the sampling was performed once a month from March to September 2021. Pollinators were collected using the sweepnet technique, placed in a sterile tube, and stored in a refrigerator until arrival at the laboratory, then the species of all individuals were identified and investigated. Each sample was analysed individually, and DNA and RNA were extracted as previously reported (MAZZEI *et al.*, 2019; CILIA *et al.*, 2020). The investigated pathogens were: *Nosema ceranae*, *Nosema apis*, *Paenibacillus larvae*, *Melissococcus plutonius*, *Crithida mellificae*, *Lotmaria passim*, *Crithidia bombi*, *Ascospaera apis*, *Spiroplasma apis*, *Spiroplasma mellifirum*, Kashmir bee virus (KBV), Deformed wing virus (DWV), Acute bee paralysis virus (ABPV), Israeli acute paralysis virus (IAPV), Black queen cell virus (BQCV), Sac brood

virus (SBV), Chronic bee paralysis virus (CBPV), Slow bee paralysis virus (SBPV), *Apis mellifera* filamentous virus (*AmFV*), *Apis* iridescent virus (AIV) and Moku virus.

Both extracted nucleic acids were analysed using qPCR following the protocols for either gene sequence. DNA previously extracted from positive honey bee samples was used as positive controls, while sterile water was used as a negative control in all analytical steps.

A total of 1028 specimens were sampled, identified, and analysed for the above-mentioned pathogens. In total, only 13 pathogens were detected. No IAPV, AIV, SBPV, Moku virus, *N. apis*, *C. mellificae*, *P. larvae* and *M. plutonius* were detected. Overall, high positive individuals were found (63.9%), and *N. ceranae*, DWV, and CBPV were the most prevalent pathogens. Considering all positive individuals, a mean abundance of 5.15×10^6 was found, while the CBPV copies number resulted the highest (8.63×10^7), followed by *N. ceranae* (1.58×10^7) and BQCV (4.84×10^6). The spillover events were also indicated by the replicative form of viruses that were founded in all positive individuals. Besides sequence analysis indicated that the same genetic variants were circulating in the same site or regions. The data showed a specific trend in prevalence and abundance. A high prevalence was found in March, which rapidly decreased in April and increase month by month reaching its peak in September. On the other hand, pathogen abundance reached its peak in July, after a constantly increase during each sampling month.

This is the first study investigating the circulation of honey bee pathogen in wild pollinators in Italy. The results encourage the deployment of monitoring programmes to improve our understanding of the interspecific spillover events among the pollinators and better consideration of the pollinator welfare in a One-Health approach (WILFERT *et al.*, 2021).

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